

Analysing the legislative framework effects on the e-arbitration for the resolution of the e-commerce disputes in Jordan

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Abstract

Electronic Arbitration is considered as the most effective means for the resolution of the disputes in the organization. The electronic arbitration is similar to the traditional arbitration in many ways. The statement of the problem can be articulated on the fact that it is based on the grounds that create different commercial disputes that are developed on regular basis. The research aims to know about the legislation to look for the development of the appropriate legislation for preserving the rights of the companies and resolving the differences effectively. The main purpose of this research is to know the extent to which the electronic arbitration and the processes linked have an influence on the settlement of the disputes that are formed on the electronic basis. Thus, this research will use of primary and secondary qualitative to achieve aim and objectives of research.

Keywords: Electronic Arbitration, conventional arbitration, disputes, legislative Frameworks.

1. Introduction

Electronic Arbitration is regarded as the major concept of resolution of the major disputes in the organizations. The electronic arbitration and traditional arbitration are similar in many aspects. There are various proceedings that are carried out in different parts of the world virtually. Arbitration is used as the substitute alternative dispute resolution method and the majority of the parties aim at the negotiation of the matters before filing any major suits in the court. The arbitrary claim can be filed by the arbitrary clause in the agreement that is signed by both the parties. Electronic Arbitration is the Alternative Dispute Resolution method (ADR) and it comprises of the Online Dispute Resolution technique (ODR). Fundamentally, it can be considered that both the online and the electronic arbitration are similar and both of them include the arbitration in the international

telecommunications. Mania (2015) stated that electronic arbitration could be clearly discriminated by using the modern means of communication that is dependent on the communication technology and the information. It includes the internet, which also comprises of the network use in the board range of various legal transactions.

2. Statement of Problem

The statement of problem is articulated which is dependent on the grounds that creates various commercial disputes that are developed on the daily basis. Other than that, it allows the legislator to look for the development of the suitable legislation for the preservation of the rights of the companies and resolve their differences in an effective manner. The underlying purpose behind this research is the explanation of the role of electronic arbitration in the preservation of the rights of the companies. The major problem that will be discussed in this study is the extension of arbitration starting from local to regional and then international [1]. The main focus of this research will be on the consideration of the ways in which the present trade disputed among the organizations can be handled on the local, regional and international level by the electronic arbitration. The major research questions that will be discussed in this study include the following:

- What are the legislative framework in Jordan and the main features from which the arbitration laws can be derived easily?
- What are the major aspects of the present legislative framework that have an impact on the enforceability of the e-arbitration for the resolution of the e-commerce in Jordan?
- How can be the e-arbitration can incorporate into the arbitration and e-commerce procedures in Jordan?

3. Aim & Objectives Of Research

The major aim of this research is to assess the extent to which the electronic arbitration and its process have an impact on the settlement of the disputes by the determination of the factors that are the mechanisms and means which are followed on an electronic basis [2]. Moreover, the research aims at depicting the role of the electronic arbitration in the preservation of the rights of the organization. The research also aims at the creation and establishment of the confidence in the mechanisms and means in an effective manner. The major objective of this study is to assess the limit up to which the organizations and the business can solve the disputes by the electronic arbitration. The efficacy of electronic arbitration in the international arena will be considered in this research.

4. Literature Review

Lee (2017) explained in his study that electronic arbitration is regarded as the most effective means of dealing with the judicial procedures in the trade disputes. It is regarded as the efficient and effective process that is linked with the litigation. The international agreements are the common thing in the modification of the arbitration clause for solving any type of differences that can occur during that contract. Negi (2016) further discussed that law and litigation enforcement occurs on the voluntary basis of the true principles. On the other hand, Ribeiro (2017) argued that electronic arbitration procedure is the contract among the two parties that are present in the actual conduct of the business. The agreement among two or more than two parties can help in resolving the major conflicts that are linked with the electronic arbitration. The two main traditional concepts that are linked with electronic arbitration include the arbitration agreement and the clause compromissaire [3]. The arbitration is the agreement, which is conducted by the parties in an independent manner and requires the effective steps for solving major issues. The clause compromissaire is an agreement, which is in the contract that provides the assignment of the future dispute that arises in the form of arbitrator.

Wolff (2017) mentioned that electronic arbitration starts with the electronic contract for solving the major disputes of the organization. Fayad (2015) indicated in his study that electronic arbitration is the process, which is the substitute process for the fulfilment of the parties and arbitrators.

5. Methodology

This research study will make use of the qualitative and the data for conducting the research will be conducted from the primary and secondary resources for knowing about the electronic arbitration. There are different techniques, which will be utilized for the interpretation of the techniques that are used for collecting and comprehending the secondary data of various studies. In accordance to the study by Fayyad (2015), qualitative research is characterized in a suitable manner and it will make use of methods and techniques that will make the study easier. The methods and techniques will point out the main topic of the study and the researcher will help in knowing about the overall view of electronic arbitration. The qualitative research in this study will help in the particular methodology that will be used for the improved understanding of arbitration concept. Negi (2016) defined the research concepts in an effective manner to provide support to the researcher for adopting and implementing the right objectives. This research will make use of the qualitative research methods for the data collection and analysis of the data in different aspects that are associated with the electronic arbitration [4].

6. Analysis and Findings

There are various studies that are linked with the electronic arbitration many researchers observe the Electronic arbitration and it makes use of the electronic methods into the arbitration. Ribeiro (2017) stated that electronic arbitration and the requirements of the procedures make sure to adopt and implement the technology particularly the international arbitration. Lee (2017) explained that Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) system includes the arbitration to the maximum extent. Mania (2015) also indicated in his study that online arbitration is not common but the document only arbitration is common and it requires the personnel arbitrator along with the occurrence of the e-commerce dispute. Wolff (2017) also indicated in his study that the serious threat is related with the feasibility and credibility. Mania (2015) further explained that arbitration is the ideal choice for the medium-sized and small e-commerce disputes. Wolff (2017) pointed out that electronic arbitration cannot be automated including the complications associated with the difficulty of the validation of the issues related with it. Electronic arbitration has developed as the new concept form the conventional arbitration and it is compatible with the electronic transactions. Ribeiro (2017) mentioned in his study that it is important to finish the arbitration processes by using the effective communication means. Electronic arbitration and the

procedures related with it are not concerned with the physical presence by the arbitrators and it ends with issuing the electronic judgements as well [5].

5. Summary and Conclusion

Hence, it can be concluded that there are various ways by which the organizations can resolve the disputes that are related with the electronic arbitration. This research evaluated the influence of electronic arbitration on the settlement of the disputes by knowing the factors that are the means and mechanisms, which are followed on an electronic basis. The factors that are linked with the identification of the obstacles and providing the solutions are implemented in the legal framework. The qualitative research method was used in this paper for conducting the research by making use secondary and primary resources and knowing about the major concept linked with the electronic arbitration.

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